

اشاعت اسلام کے اصول و آداب (قرآن و حدیث اور اسوہ رسول ﷺ کی روشنی میں)

Publication of Islamic principles and manners (In the light of Quran, Hadith and Uswa-e-Rasool ﷺ)

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Abstract

In this article propagation and publication of Islam and its principles have been explained that how the Holy Prophet obeyed the religion and told the people that Islam guides every aspect of human life which is called Sharia, and the main purpose of this education is to convey the message of Allah to the people and Allah should be considered as Lord. In his attributes, powers, and rights no one should be involved while explaining the principle of invitation and preaching it has been said that people should be called to the path of Allah with wisdom and good sermons and polite language should be used in arguments. In the eyes of Allah, the only action is acceptable to him which is done for his pleasure from this point of view, the religion Islam has a unique place in the world because in Islam people are called to goodness and prevented from evil so that an abstract society can be formed. Our aim is to share Islam to others with selves' improvement.

Keywords: Publication of Islam, Rules, Manners, Message of Allah, Quran, Hadith

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